

An Observational Study to Assess the Effect of Attachable Intra Oral Wound Dressing Tape on Post Extraction Dental Socket

Sourav Kumar¹, Dipti Nayak²

¹Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, NMCH, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, RDJMMCH, Turki, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

Received: 09-12-2023 / Revised: 15-01-2024 / Accepted: 23-02-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Dipti Nayak

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the effect of Attachable intra oral wound dressing tape on post extraction dental socket.

Methods: The study was conducted as a prospective, randomized, controlled, and single-blind clinical trial in the Department of Dentistry, NMCH, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar, India. The study took place over a period of year. The approval includes a unique registration number and adherence to the instructions outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. A total of 58 teeth in 58 patients were enrolled in this study.

Results: The patients included 31 with (49.2%) percent females, and 27 with (42.9%) percent males and a mean age of 30 years (range, 15-65). Most teeth were located in the mandible (74.6%, n= 47) and (17.5%, n =11) in maxilla. The demographic distribution regarding the age, sex, and jaw at a Mean \pm SD (30.30 \pm 11.210). Based on postoperative assessments, the data show great percent (65.5%, n= 19) of normal bleeding grade in a study group with a p value of 0.001 so result showed statistically significant difference in the study group when compared with the control group regarding the post dental extraction bleeding. Regarding the incidence of alveolar osteitis after 4 days post dental extraction, the result show 5 cases of alveolar osteitis in control group with (17.2%) percent, and 2 cases of alveolar osteitis in study group (6.9%) with a statistically significant difference in the decrease of alveolar ostietis incidence in study group with a p value = 0.000.

Conclusion: Ora-aid is a dental product that can be used after a dental procedure to safeguard the blood clot in the dental socket and prevent it from being dislodged within the initial 5-6 hours following the tooth extraction.

Keywords: ORA-AID, post extraction bleeding, alveolar osteitis

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The skin and oral mucosa are crucial barriers against exogenous substances, pathogens, and mechanical stresses. [1] Compared to the healing of cutaneous wounds, wound healing of the oral mucosa proceeds quickly and leaves less scar formation. [2,3] The causes of mucosal wounds are classified as physical, chemical, and thermal. Physical and mechanical traumas of the oral mucosa include linea alba, chronic biting, epulis fissuratum, and inflammatory papillary hyperplasia. Chemical injuries of the oral mucosa include chemical burns, post-anesthetic ulceration of the hard palate, and contact allergic stomatitis. [4]

Topical treatment is more effective than systemic treatment for healing physical traumas and chemical injuries in the oral mucosa. [5] Various topical treatments, such as adhesive tablets, gels, and films, have been developed for oral wound healing. [6] Among these treatment types, films possess properties such as adhesiveness and flexibility and

protect the wound surfaces, reducing pain and increasing treatment effectiveness. [7,8]

The attachable oral wound dressing tape is a novel method of securing an intraoral patch to safeguard areas affected by procedures such as tooth extraction, implant surgery, orthodontics, and ulcers. It consists of a hydrophilic polymer complex and a mucoadhesive layer. The mucoadhesive layer interacts with the moisture in the oral mucosa, transforming into a gel-like state and partially expanding. This process aids in maintaining the moisture level of the wound by absorbing exudate and minor bleeding. The attachable oral wound dressing tab is extremely pliable, securely adhering to the surface of the oral wound, and causes a minimal sensation of a foreign object. Mucoadhesion persists until the hydrophilic polymer dissolves, after which the outer layer is naturally removed from the mucosa within approximately 6-8 hours later. [9-12]

The aim of the present study was to assess the effect of Attachable intra oral wound dressing tape on post extraction dental socket.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted as a prospective, randomized, controlled, and single-blind clinical trial in the Department of Dentistry, NMCH, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar, India. The study took place over a period of one year. The approval includes a unique registration number and adherence to the instructions outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. A total of 58 teeth in 58 patients were enrolled in this study.

A sample size was chosen for its convenience after performance the Clinical examination by the specialist in oral medicine in the diagnosis department, extraction difficulty assessment by oral surgeon was done at oral surgery department for every patient who had first permanent molar teeth extraction To identify suitable participants for the study. Prior to commencing the implementation of this investigation, the operators underwent specialized training in order to position the attachable oral wound dressing tape precisely on the fresh dental socket, assess the difference between dental socket oozing and bleeding after 2 hour, and the incidence of alveolar osteitis after 4 days.

The necessary information regarding the patient's medical and dental history, as well as other individual data, was obtained through a face-to-face interview with each patient. Appendix I Extraction of 1st molars for each patient was made under local anesthesia (lidocaine with adrenaline 1:80000). The patients were divided randomly into study group in it dental sockets were covered by attachable oral wound dressing tape (oral aids) and control group in it dental sockets were covered with intraoral sterilized gauze pack.

During patient selection, particular care was taken to ensure that the groups were similar with respect to age and sex in order to eliminate the possible effects of personal variables on the outcome of study.

A signed statement of informed consent was obtained from each patient before to their participation in the trial. Parents/caregivers provided their approval for patients who were below the age of 18 by signing the informed consent declaration.

Appendix III Inclusion Criteria

1. Patient without any history of bleeding disorders.
2. Patient without any history of uncontrolled disease.
3. Person without any history of allergy to dental anesthesia.
4. Patient with first molar permanent tooth indicated for atraumatic dental extraction.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patient with history of bleeding disorders.
2. Patient with history of uncontrolled disease.
3. Patient with history of allergy to dental anesthesia.
4. Patient with periapical lesion or traumatic dental extraction.

Follow up

All patients in this study was assessed

1. After 2 hour for post dental extraction bleeding, the grade 0 (very low), grade 1 (low), grade 2 (normal), grade 3 (high), and grade 4 (very high)
2. After 4 days to assess the post extraction dental socket healing (alveolar osteitis) as present or not.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristic

Age	Frequency	Percent
15-24	21	36.2
25-34	22	37.9
35-44	11	19.0
>44	4	6.9
total	58	100.0
Sex	Frequency	Percent
Female	31	49.2
Male	27	42.9
Total	58	100.0
Jaw	Frequency	Percent
Maxilla	11	17.5
Mandible	47	74.6
Total	58	100.0

The patients included 31 with (49.2%) percent females and 27 with (42.9%) percent males and a mean age of 30 years (range, 15-65). Most teeth were located in the mandible (74.6%, n= 47) and (17.5%, n =11) in maxilla. The demographic distribution regarding the age, sex, and jaw at a Mean \pm SD (30.30 \pm 11.210).

Table 2: Post dental extraction bleeding

Bleeding	Very low N (%)	Low N (%)	Normal N (%)	High N (%)	Very high N (%)	P value
Study group	0(0%)	18(62.1)	9(31.0)	2(6.9)	0(0%)	0.001
Control group	0(0%)	6(20.7)	19(65.5)	4(13.8)	0(0%)	

Based on postoperative assessments, the data show great percent (65.5%, n= 19) of normal bleeding grade in a study group with a p value of 0.001 so result showed statistically significant difference in the study group when compared with the control group regarding the post dental extraction bleeding.

Table 3: Alveolar osteitis

Alveolar osteitis	N (%)	P value
Study group	2(6.9)	0.000
Control group	5(17.2)	

Regarding the incidence of alveolar osteitis after 4 days post dental extraction, the result show 5 cases of alveolar osteitis in control group with (17.2%) percent, and 2 cases of alveolar osteitis in study group (6.9%) with a statistically significant difference in the decrease of alveolar osteitis incidence in study group with a p value = 0.000.

Discussion

Following a tooth extraction, it is typical for the extraction site to experience bleeding. Patients should be aware that it is common for the area to release a small amount of fluid for up to 24 hours following the treatment. Post-extraction bleeding (PEB) refers to the abnormal condition where bleeding persists without the development of blood clots or extends beyond a duration of 8 to 12 hours. Patients experiencing such bleeding occurrences may require immediate dental consultations and procedures, which can be distressing. The reasons of post-extraction bleeding (PEB) can originate from a specific area, result from a systemic condition, be triggered by medication, or occur due to the patient's failure to follow post-extraction recommendations. In order to manage this bleeding, many local and systemic approaches have been employed, relying on the proficiency of the clinician. [13]

The patients included 31 with (49.2%) percent females, and 27 with (42.9%) percent males and a mean age of 30 years (range, 15-65). Most teeth were located in the mandible (74.6%, n= 47) and (17.5%, n =11) in maxilla. The demographic distribution regarding the age, sex, and jaw at a Mean \pm SD (30.30 \pm 11.210). Based on postoperative assessments, the data show great percent (65.5%, n= 19) of normal bleeding grade in a study group with a p value of 0.001 so result showed statistically significant difference in the study group when compared with the control group regarding the post dental extraction bleeding. ORA-AID is a new concept of attaching an intraoral patch or tape to protect the affected area such as post extraction, implant surgery, orthodontics and ulcers. [9]

ORA-AID is composed of 2 layers: an oral mucosa adhesive side and a protection side. When exposed to moisture, the water-soluble adhesive side changes into a gel state to achieve adhesion to the wound area for approximately 6 hours. The protection side consists of a non-resorbable polymer which covers the wound to protect it from the environment in the oral cavity. It is Protects intraoral wounds from food, bacteria, and cigarette smoke, Aids in hemostasis, besides it is Easy to cut and shape and Strong adhesive using hydrophilic polymer. [13] Regarding the incidence of alveolar osteitis after 4 days post dental extraction, the result show 5 cases of alveolar osteitis in control group with (17.2%) percent, and 2 cases of alveolar osteitis in study group (6.9%) with a statistically significant difference in the decrease of alveolar osteitis incidence in study group with a p value = 0.000. The study found a statistically significant difference in wound healing and dry socket formation between the study group and the control group. This difference may be attributed to the mucoadhesion, which is a result of various mechanisms including the conversion of the inner layer of ora aid into a body glue. [14] This mucoadhesion helps in promoting the proper healing of the dental socket. This aligns with the findings of Makvandi, Pooyan, et al [15], who demonstrated that the OWD film's effective mucoadhesion has significant promise in minimizing wound infections and enhancing tissue repair.

Conclusion

Ora-aid is a dental product that can be used after a dental procedure to safeguard the blood clot in the dental socket and prevent it from being dislodged within the initial 5-6 hours following the tooth extraction. Furthermore, patients will have significant enhancement in their comfort, less postoperative pain and bleeding, safeguarding of intraoral wounds against food, bacteria, and cigarette smoke, and facilitation of recovery following oral surgery and treatment. No significant problems or morbidity were observed in this study regarding the use of ora-aids, except for difficulties in adhering to the prescribed regimen, which were

found to be connected with the educational level of the patients.

References

1. Presland RB, Jurevic RJ. Making sense of the epithelial barrier: what molecular biology and genetics tell us about the functions of oral mucosal and epidermal tissues. *J Dent Educ.* 2002;66(4):564–574.
2. Szpaderska AM, Zuckerman JD, DiPietro LA. Differential injury responses in oral mucosal and cutaneous wounds. *J Dent Res.* 2003;82(8):621–626.
3. Warburton G, Nares S, Angelov N, Brahim JS, Dionne RA, Wahl SM. Transcriptional events in a clinical model of oral mucosal tissue injury and repair. *Wound Repair Regen.* 2005;13(1):19–26.
4. Koray M, Tosun T. 2019. Oral Mucosal Trauma and Injuries. *Trauma in Dentistry.*
5. Katz J, Langevitz P, Shemer J, Barak S, Livneh A. Prevention of recurrent aphthous stomatitis with colchicine: an open trial. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 1994;31(3 Pt 1):459–461.
6. Lee JW, Park JH, Robinson JR. Bioadhesive-based dosage forms: the next generation. *J Pharm Sci.* 2000;89(7):850–866.
7. Peh KK, Wong CF. Polymeric films as vehicle for buccal delivery: swelling, mechanical, and bioadhesive properties. *J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 1999;2(2):53–61.
8. Mahdi AB, Coulter WA, Woolfson AD, Lamey PJ. Efficacy of bioadhesive patches in the treatment of recurrent aphthous stomatitis. *J Oral Pathol Med.* 1996;25(8):416–419.
9. Kang S, Jang EJ, Jo HM, Kang SS, Lee MS, Yun SY, et al. Effects of a Topically Applied Oral Wound Dressing Film on Intra-oral Wound Healing in Rabbits. *In vivo.* 2022;36(4):1745-1752.
10. Lam MT, Nauta A, Meyer NP, Wu JC, Longaker MT, Gurtner GC. Effective delivery of stem cells using an extracellular matrix patch results in increased cell survival and proliferation and reduced scarring in skin wound healing. *Tissue Engineering Part A.* 2013;19(5- 6):738-747.
11. Liang Y, Kiick KL. Mussel-inspired, antibacterial, conductive, antioxidant, injectable composite hydrogel wound dressing to promote the regeneration of infected skin. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science.* 2019;556:514-528.
12. Seiyeong YUN. Film for oral hemostasis and wound protection. U.S. Patent No. 10,582,915; c2020 Mar 10.
13. Nagraj SK, Prashanti E, Aggarwal H, Lingappa A, Muthu MS, Krishanappa SK, Hassan H. Interventions for treating post-extraction bleeding. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews;* c2018, 3.
14. Seiyeong YU, inventor; TBM Co, assignee. Film for oral hemostasis and wound protection. United States patent US 10,582,915. 2020 Mar 10.
15. Khutoryanskiy VV. Advances in mucoadhesion and mucoadhesive polymers. *Macromolecular Bioscience.* 2011;11(6):748-764.